

D6.1 COLLABORATION WITH EU PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES (1)

Project: Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable Agriculture

Supported by Earth Observation

Acronym: ENVISION

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869366.

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	869366	Acronym	ENVISION	
Full Title	Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable Agriculture Supported by Earth Observation			
Start Date	1 st September 2020	Duration	36 months	
Project URL	https://envision-h2020.eu/			
Deliverable	D6.1 Collaboration with EU projects and initiatives (1)			
Work Package	WP6 – Commercialisation and exploitation			
Date of Delivery	Contractual	30/6/2021	Actual	30/6/2021
Nature	Report	Dissemination Level	Public	
Lead Beneficiary	ETAM			
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Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
D0.1	23/6/2021	Draft	Draft version sent to reviewers for comments and input	Mr Manolis Tsantakis (ETAM)
D0.2	26/6/2021	Draft reviewed	Comments/Input received from reviewers	Mr Daniel Copot (ITC)
F1.0	28/6/2021	Final	Integration of input	Mr Manolis Tsantakis (ETAM)

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1 Executive summary

ENVISION has established connections with 8 relevant projects by carrying out introductory online meetings with projects' presentations and initial discussions and exchange of views. The fields of potential collaboration that were proposed by ENVISION include joint meetings, events and activities, formal provision of advice, exchange of information, joint use of EC services and cooperation regarding the projects' available communication channels. The main outcome is that all 8 projects are open for further discussions in due course. However, there are also fields already recognised as having a strong potential and relevant discussions were quite focused.

The next relevant deliverable D6.5 "Collaboration with EU projects and initiatives (2)" is due in month 20 and will further elaborate on the solutions derived from the projects, the ENVISION strengths and potential contributions from the other projects.

2 Introduction

The "terms of reference" for the present deliverable are clearly described in the project proposal as follows:

ENVISION has to "...establish the necessary liaison connections with the most prominent EU projects, agricultural related projects funded under the same call, as well as with the e-shape project. Through this task, a review and mapping of ICT solutions and EO based services derived from these projects will be conducted (in collaboration with WP2, Task 2.1) in order to evaluate how these products could contribute to ENVISION, which are the main ENVISION's strengths and how complementary these solutions are with regards to ENVISION. The first deliverable will include the established liaison and connections with the most EU projects, agricultural related projects funded under the same call as well as with the e-shape project".

In this first deliverable the work carried out concerns the specification of methods of potential collaboration, a general overview of the relevant projects, and the reporting on the first contacts that took place.

Under the same call as ENVISION are currently funded the projects **FIRE**, **EC-NEXTLAND**, **SAFERS** and **SUSTUNTECH**. However, only **FIRE** and **EC-NEXTLAND** are relevant to agriculture.

Eleven (11) more projects have been recorded as relevant and potential for collaboration, summing up to thirteen (13) in total.

CALLISTO

<https://callisto-h2020.eu>

EUXDAT

<https://www.euxdat.eu>

candela

<https://candela-h2020.eu>

**MEF
4CAP**

<https://mef4cap.eu>

DIONE

<https://dione-project.eu>

NIVA
NEW IACS VISION IN ACTION

<https://www.niva4cap.eu>

EO4AGR

<https://eo4agri.eu/>

sen4cap
common agricultural policy

<http://esa-sen4cap.org>

On the 26th of March 2021, 10 written invitations were sent to the following projects: EUROPABON, DIONE, NIVA, EO4AGRI, EUXDAT, SEN4CAP, CANDELA, Fire-Forum, EC-NEXTLAND and VITIGEOSS. Later, on the 25th of May 2021, an invitation was sent to the MEF4CAP project.

Collaboration with ENVISION H2020 project

Manolis Tsantakis
 Προς @ears.org
 Ιδιωτ. κοιν. ifigenia Tsoutsia

Παρ 26/3/2021 2:29 μμ

 Να μη γίνεται ποτέ μετάφραση από τα: Αγγλικά

Dear Fire-Forum colleague,

The ENVISION Horizon 2020 project "Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable Agriculture Supported by Earth Observation" aims to fulfil the need for continuous and systematic monitoring of agricultural land, shifting the focus from fragmented monitoring limited to specific fields and dates to territory-wide and all-year-round monitoring. Therefore, the ENVISION services address impacts stemming from unsustainable agricultural activities, i.e. soil degradation, biodiversity loss, landscape degradation, GHG emissions and water pollution and support farmers towards compliance to different environmental and good agricultural practice rules.

Specifically, ENVISION develops and pilot tests innovative tools for the continuous, large scale and uninterrupted monitoring of farm management activities with regards to sustainability, in compliance with the CAP's agri-environmental objectives.

The project makes use of heterogeneous types of available data and state-of-the-art technologies for providing a fully automated and scalable toolbox of services to monitor agricultural practices all year round.

It also uses in situ, open data and historical information, as well as data made available by GEOSS and Copernicus.

This information is used to develop cultivated crop type maps and to monitor soil organic carbon, vegetation status and crop growth.

Given our relevant objectives and tools of research, and the overarching goal for a more competitive and sustainable European agri-food sector, we would like to invite you to establish an open channel of knowledge exchange and hopefully cooperation to promote science, research and development.

If this proposal in principle is also deemed useful from your side, we can organize an online meeting for a further discussion.

Kind regards,

EMMANOUIL TSANTAKIS

In the meantime, connections have been established with e-shape, while a decision was taken to contact the CALLISTO project later, given that it has been recently kick-started.

Regarding e-shape, between October 2020 and April 2021 a series of meetings took place (28/10/2020, 10/12/2020, 24/3/2021, 16/4/2021), led from the side of ENVISION by the University of Reading.

In regard to the invitations sent on March 26, seven (7) projects accepted to meet with ENVISION, and the respective meetings took place during May and June on the following dates:

EO4AGRI	7/5/2021
VITIGEOSS	13/5/2021
FIRE	17/5/2021
EUROPABON	24/5/2021
NIVA	31/5/2021
MEF4CAP	4/6/2021
SEN4CAP	17/6/2021

The rest of the projects (DIONE, EUXDAT, CANDELA, NEXTLAND) did not reply to the ENVISION's invitation.

3 Methods of potential collaboration and initial action plan

Following a preparatory work, during the meetings that were held, ENVISION presented to the other projects the following possibilities to consider in regard to collaboration:

- High-level workshops (e.g. Coordinators' meetings, Technical groups' meetings)
- Joint activities (e.g. common (final) events, webinars, policy sessions, joint newsletters, online editions, publications and press releases, hosting of articles)
- Collaboration regarding user requirements
- Advisory services (e.g. Formal advisors to each other)
- Joint use of the Horizon Results Booster services
- Exchange of information on stakeholders' mapping
- Projects' social media connected and mutually supported.

However, a further set of possibilities has been already processed and, in the future might be put on the “table” of discussions. Namely, the following organisational and performance management options:

- specify, in writing, a short roadmap and particularly specific goals (“aspirations” of collaboration),
- set smart objectives (most importantly measurable and time specific objectives),
- specify a wider set of joint activities,
- define output indicators (numerical values for the outputs of collaboration) and result indicators (tangible/measurable results).

In other words, instead of a “vague” collaboration, this may have a specific “framework” of operations and indicators of success.

4 Brief presentations of the targeted projects

Starting with the projects of the same call, FIRE and NEXTLAND are presented.

 FIRE FIRE's main objective is to unleash the potential that EO can bring to society by boosting the innovativeness, productivity and competitiveness of businesses. It promotes the adoption of EO solutions in various sectors and among them agriculture. FIRE is the first initiative fully dedicated to bringing actors from key commercial sectors together, outlining the perspectives of their market and using these insights to shape a strategic roadmap for the EO downstream sector. The project is going to establish a user community in agriculture (and other sectors) and a dedicated "EO Evangelist" programme to promote the adoption of EO solutions. Open dialogue with the demand side will guide the development, delivery and uptake of EO services. To identify user needs in its focus sectors, FIRE will organise focus group discussions with stakeholders. Two types of events will facilitate the dialogue within the focus sectors, i.e. the Focus Group Events and the Fire-Forum that will take place twice within the 3-year duration of the project. Moreover, to reach these stakeholders, the FIRE project will partner with Sector Leads that represent the sector and its value chain. COPA-COGECA is the Sector Lead for agriculture and will leverage its network towards improving the adoption of EO solutions. <https://fire-forum.eu/> [start date 12/2019, end date 11/2022].

 NEXTLAND The focus of NextLand regarding the use of EO services in agriculture is on the support to irrigation, crop planning optimisation, early stress and anomaly detection, improved crop monitoring and yield prediction. The project is going to develop on a single platform 15 co-created, innovative and operational land management services (e.g. biomass production, crop phenology, crop type classification, crop water needs, anomaly detection, evapotranspiration, soil moisture, vegetation indexes, vegetation water content) based on GEOSS and Copernicus data to strengthen the value chain of the agricultural (and forestry) sector. These commercial midstream EO based services will be offered under a common service delivery platform. <https://ec-nextland.eu/> [start date 6/2020, end date 5/2023].

The rest of the relevant projects include both running and ended projects.

 CALLISTO CALLISTO aims to bridge the gap between Copernicus Data and Information Access Services (DIAS) providers and application end-users through dedicated Artificial Intelligence (AI) solutions. The project will provide an interoperable Big Data platform integrating EO data deriving from the DIAS with crowdsourced, geo-referenced and distributed data from various sources. All data will be served in Mixed Reality environments. Furthermore, CALLISTO will develop an in-season availability of parcel-level crop type information using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data, aiming to identify, across a large area, parcels that potentially do not comply with CAP rules that are then targeted for inspection during a one-day field survey with Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV). CALLISTO will make use of Deep Learning to perform large-scale parcel-level crop classification and outlier detection for grassland. The trained

models will then be loaded on the UAV mounted machine to produce near-real time inference at the edge. Monitoring will be accomplished using the collection and analysis of several types of heterogeneous and large data collections, such as UAV imagery, geo-tagged photos and street-level imagery from vehicles. Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies will also be involved in the data analysis in order to support EU implementation bodies and policymakers in EU CAP monitoring.

<https://callisto-h2020.eu/> [start date 1/2021, end date 12/2023].

CANDELA project was born with the aim of providing services that facilitate and exploit the usage of Copernicus data building on top of the DIAS. Four (4) analytics tools were deployed in CREODIAS: i) Earth Observation data mining for classification and change detection, ii) Deep Learning for change detection on time series for optical and radar Earth observation data, iii) Semantic search and indexation on the output of the Earth observation library and non-image data, iv) Data fusion techniques to merge pre-processed data from various sources. Two out of the four use-cases concerned a) urban expansion and agriculture, aimed at studying the effect of urban expansion on agricultural areas due to the continuous development of human settlements and climate changes, and b) change detection in vineyards, assessing damage level caused by natural hazards. Robust and generic data analytics tools and various remote sensing data sources were used to detect changes of interest and using data analytics tools with remote sensing data in order to quantify the damages caused by natural hazards to vineyards.

<https://candela-h2020.eu/> [start date 5/2018, end date 10/2020].

DIONE project is developing a direct payment controlling toolbox for paying agencies to abide by the modernised CAP regulations, involving novel techniques that will improve the capabilities of satellite technology while integrating various data sources (drones, soil sensors and mobile applications). A system developed on a regional or national scale will evaluate the monitored parameters to form evidence-based conclusions regarding eventual environmental impacts on an entire region. DIONE aims to a) capitalise on results of SEN4CAP project that showcased the capability of Sentinel data to monitor the crop diversification rules, b) include in the analysis the so far neglected EFA types (fallow land of all sizes, buffer strips, hedges, trees), by making use of super-resolution technology that improves the 10-20m Sentinel resolution to an improved resolution range (5-10m), c) complement the use of EO data with a system of reliable, ground-based geo-tagged photos captured by the farmers that exploits advances that allow for improved positional accuracy, low-footprint encryption techniques for improved data security and reliability and image detecting manipulation techniques (image forensics), d) implement a green compliance toolbox integrated with the paying agencies' tools. <https://dione-project.eu/> [start date 1/2020, end date 6/2022].

In the frames of a series of major reforms of the CAP, the paying agencies were asked to adopt new working methods, such as the use of remote monitoring mechanisms as a substitute for on-the-spot inspections or the application of EO data to enable payment for performance instead of paying for compliance. The EO4AGRI methodology was a combination of community building, service gap analysis, technology watch, strategic research agenda design and policy recommendations. Its focus

was the provision of tools to improve the European capacity on operational agriculture monitoring based on information derived from Copernicus satellite observation data and through the exploitation of associated geospatial and socio-economic information services. Its outcomes were a white paper including a policy roadmap, a cooperation framework and a strategic research agenda to provide the European Commission and other authorities with actionable recommendations for improvements on the use of COPERNICUS data and services in agriculture, design of future European research programmes and transversal initiatives. <https://eo4agri.eu/> [start date 11/2018, end date 10/2020].

e-shape, a flagship European project, is the largest coordinated effort to highlight operational services in the field of Earth observation research in Europe and aiming to improve user uptake of Earth Observation data. Numerous cloud-based pilot applications under certain thematic areas address societal challenges, foster entrepreneurship, and support sustainable development. The showcase on Food Security and Sustainable Agriculture consists of pilots showcasing that Copernicus data sets combined with the necessary in-situ data, weather and soil data can deliver improved information at the global, national and local scale, exploiting the processing infrastructures offered by Copernicus DIAS. The foreseen outcomes include i) sets of algorithms, ii) smart farming products and services, such as crop classification, crop growth indices, dynamic phenology estimation, phenology forecasting, yield estimation and yield damage assessment, iii) an NDVI-based Crop Insurance product, iv) an upgraded platform providing EO-based information to the potato growers and industry, v) means for improved vineyard and orchard decision support systems, and vi) assessment of SDG indicators. <https://e-shape.eu/> [start date 5/2019, end date 4/2023].

EUROPABON adopts the approach for the development of coordinated Biodiversity Observation Networks (BONs) from the Group on Earth Observations Biodiversity Observation Network (GEO BON). The approach emphasizes co-design with stakeholders at all stages of the BON development, from assessment of current monitoring to implementation of a new design including new information streams. EUROPABON aims at integrating data streams with models to produce relevant biodiversity indicators for policy and management, assessments and scenarios building on the Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) and Essential Ecosystem Service Variables (EESVs) developed in GEO BON. EuropaBON's mission is to overcome existing data gaps and workflow bottlenecks by designing an EU-wide framework for monitoring biodiversity and ecosystem services. EuropaBON will engage users to identify the data needs of policies and targets aligned with the new European Green Deal. The project will design a new structure for monitoring biodiversity and ecosystem services and model essential variables to integrate different reporting streams, data sources and monitoring strategies. Moreover, it will deliver solid knowledge about the dimensions of biodiversity change across space and time to support decision-making, and will assess existing monitoring efforts, identify user and policy needs, and investigate the feasibility of a European coordination center of monitoring operations. <http://europabon.org/> [start date 12/2020, end date 11/2023].

EUXDAT proposed an e-Infrastructure which addressed agriculture, land monitoring and energy efficiency for sustainable development as a way to support planning policies. Furthermore, EUXDAT proposed solutions for crops monitoring, improving land use maps, taking better decisions on the crops to exploit in certain types of soil and improving the management of farms in general. As an e-Infrastructure for Large Data Analytics-as-a-Service, aimed at bringing heterogeneous data sources (Copernicus, climate data, sensors data, UAVs data, machinery data, land use data, hydrology data, etc.) together with advanced data analysis tools, which can make use of both Cloud and HPC resources, in order to process huge amounts of data which will be useful for supporting agriculture. EUXDAT platform offers a set of data access connectors to a large number of datasets: Copernicus data (through Mundi web services platform), Open land use map, DEM, Hydrology data and more generally OpenStreetMap datasets, LPIS (Land Parcel Identification System), Climate data (Copernicus CDS), access to Soil maps datasets, private data upload, meteorological data, field sensor data and UAV data. <https://www.euxdat.eu> [start date 11/2017, end date 10/2020].

MEF4CAP aims to identify future needs for sustainability information from different stakeholders in the agri-food sector and connect them with technological developments to improve monitoring. The project builds on several other EU level research projects, e.g., satellite innovations from projects such as SEN4CAP to modernise farm level data collection in the scope of FADN and the proposed FSDN. The project is implementing four demonstration cases to explore the potential of new technologies: benefitting from increased digitalisation of financial/administrative processes in the agrifood sector and the voluntary exchange; addressing limitations of Earth Observation addressed with sensor networks at farm level; linking national datasets for broader use in policy evaluation and integrating agri-environmental data for different purposes. One of the cases is exploring solutions to collect information from different existing sources for the certification and inspection in organic farming. Through these demonstration cases and the assessment of potential and limitations, MEF4CAP will connect future needs with technological opportunities and will contribute to the development of better CAP evaluation frameworks. <https://mef4cap.eu/> [start date 10/2020, end date 9/2023].

The objective of NIVA is to analyse and propose how IACS could be modernised and improved for the new CAP through the use of Earth Observation. NIVA applies the technological innovations from a range of projects including Sen4CAP. Beyond that it aims to improve the farmer performance assessment which is measured through indicators at the farm level. The long-term vision is to move from an annual cycle towards a multi-annual evaluation of agri-environmental and climate measures. From the experience of NIVA so far it is concluded that IACS is very valuable to assess indicators but needs further development in terms of format, accessibility, dynamism of parcels and harmonization to be useful for analysis. Furthermore, data sharing from and towards IACS systems is a key practice for better evaluation. NIVA works in 9 use cases each focusing on a particular aspect of the CAP governing tools. The use case “monitoring agro-environmental indicators” deals with IACS data sharing for impact assessment in the environmental and climate domains. It looks at integrating the IACS data, Earth Observation data from

the Sentinel 1 and 2 satellite systems of the Copernicus programme and auxiliary data like soil and weather maps and farmer specific data. <https://www.niva4cap.eu> [start date 6/2019, end date 5/2022].

Sen4CAP has been set up by ESA in direct collaboration and on request from DG-Agri, DG-Grow and DG-JRC, to identify and specify EO products and services suitable to increase the efficiency, traceability as well as reducing the costs of the IACS. Moreover, to develop algorithm theoretical basis documents along with open-source code for agricultural EO products based on Sentinel 1 & 2 responding to the user requirements. The project aimed to provide evidence of how Sentinel derived information can support the modernisation and simplification of the CAP in the post 2020 timeframe, and to provide validated algorithms, products, workflows and best practices for agriculture monitoring. Four pilot cases were conducted in 7 Member States, as well as wider tested by Paying Agencies. The project proposed four products to be used by the Paying Agencies: map of crop types, growing vegetation indicators, grassland mowing detection and agricultural practices monitoring. The validation of the Earth Observation (EO) products was done through farmers data collected by Paying Agencies and visual interpretation of Planet Very High-Resolution time series. <http://esa-sen4cap.org/> [start date 5/2017, end date 3/2021].

VitiGEOSS integrates and improves existing solutions coupling satellite imagery with in-field sensors to increase the resolution and reliability of satellite information applied to all aspects of viticulture and specific wine-business operations. The main scope of the project is to make use of the potential of EO initiatives for deploying an innovative commercial information solution to optimise sustainable grapevine cultivation via decision support systems (DSS) on phenology, irrigation, fertilisation, disease and business and sustainability management. The solution of VitiGEOSS will be proven in three demo sites in Spain, Italy and Portugal, in which will be devoted a pilot vineyard for the project. The VitiGEOSS platform, deployed as a cloud-based Applications Portal, will be the first application offering integrated services for sub-seasonal and seasonal predictions, crop management, disease warnings, business operations and sustainability monitoring. <https://vitageoss.eu/> [start date 11/2020, end date 2/2024].

5 Established liaison and connections so far

The present chapter provides details on the online meetings that took place between ENVISION and the other projects.

The University of Reading ENVISION team and the ARMIINES e-shape team took the initiative to meet to exchange knowledge, experiences and to understand the different requirements of the co-production of services. So far, several scheduled meetings took place while an exchange of project deliverables and relevant to the task documents (i.e. research publications) have been helpful and supportive in understanding each other's tasks and objectives. The main topic of discussion was how the two teams could work together in developing a standardised approach (protocol) to effectively record information derived from workshops with the end to efficiently produce user stories or relevant tools that would serve the needs of the two projects as well as the developers. The University of Reading has benefited from the early discussions with the e-shape team in respect to the challenges associated with a multicultural and diverse group of stakeholders with different needs and level of services developed. The discussions with ARMINES have been around the need to effectively engage all partners during the co-production phase of the project and therefore, good practices and challenges of the e-shape project have been shared. ARMINES provided access to co-design workshop material in Athens, as well as to deliverables D2.1, D2.2, D.23 of the eShape project. The two teams have agreed to meet frequently to share experiences, knowledge and good practices.

In e-shape, NOA leads Pilot 2 (EU_CAP Support) of the Show Case 1 (Food Security and Sustainable Agriculture showcase). NOA is responsible for the coordination of this pilot undertaking the majority of the actual technical implementation and the engagement of the stakeholders. In more detail, in the e-shape's pilot S1P2 "EU-CAP Support" NOA has as primary objective to go beyond the mere compliance to the monitoring of CAP and compliance with the CAP rules and this as it focuses on actionable advice to farmers for farm performance; farm management through the development of pertinent models, using AI techniques for the dynamic prediction crop phenology and crop yield estimation. The context and motivation of this work starts with the objectives of the new Common Agricultural Policy. Agrowth, the crop monitoring platform developed in the context of the e-shape pilot, helps support viable farm income through its crop growth monitoring, natural disaster peril warning and yield estimation services. Agrowth also assists in increasing competitiveness and agricultural productivity in a sustainable way to meet the challenges of higher demand in a resource constrained and climate uncertain world. Additionally, it can potentially help in strengthening the position of the farmer in the value chain by enhancing the cooperation among farmers – providing the cooperatives an overall view of their collective farms and strengthening their resilience and performance through sharable evidence within the organization.

EO4AGRI was a CSA project, therefore not many technical details were exchanged from the earth observation point of view. Nonetheless, the colleague from EO4AGRI, Mr Karel Charvat, mentioned a clear gap in the projects, applications and directions of the EO based agriculture monitoring status quo. Specifically, the green deal priorities are not as strongly integrated into the current EO based monitoring actions, including the CAP monitoring. The farm to fork and biodiversity dimensions of the Green deal, together with the concept of digital twin earth and the Destination Earth initiative need to reframe and redefine the EO based agriculture monitoring actions. Regarding the list of potential collaborations, Mr Karel Charvat proposed that we add the theme of standardization.

The discussion started with the biodiversity regulation, the CAP pillar 2 as a possible connection between the two projects, as well as the lack of monitoring data to assess the impact of CAP on biodiversity. Other topics of discussion concerned the possible advice from EUROPABON in interpreting outputs of ENVISION, the potential collaboration in showcasing the EUROPABON feasibility studies, the ENVISION help to EUROPABON in collecting user requirements, the building of a case together, and the advantage that the University of Reading participates in both projects. ENVISION was invited to the EUROPABON event that was taking place the next day.

ENVISION was invited from NIVA to see their open outputs, code source and tools, as well as provide to them information regarding ENVISION open outputs. NIVA is going to organize new webinars after summer 2021 and ENVISION was encouraged to take part. Moreover, NIVA has a tool called “Technology watchdog” (internal publication for technology) and they asked ENVISION to provide a use case. Lastly, NIVA proposed a joint webinar together with all relevant projects (e.g. SEN4CAP, NIVA, ENVISION etc).

A survey being carried out by Vitigeoss was an immediate field of support of ENVISION to VITIGE OSS. Furthermore, ENVISION provided contact details for wine producers and producers’ organisations. Also, AGROAPPS proposed to answer the VITIGE OSS questionnaire since they have relevant requirements recorded from their own business activity. Discussions brought up the relevance of CAP measures regarding the environment with the wine sector. Also, a discussion was made on possibilities with regards to lighthouse customers to serve both projects. ENVISION also provided the DG AGRI’s list of Certification Bodies and the Paying Agencies operating in Spain. A conference, a common paper, a joint meeting, and social media support were mentioned by the VITIGE OSS Coordinator as possibilities of collaboration. Discussions also concerned the kind of satellite and other data used. Also, a hackathon/datathon was proposed by NOA as a field of cooperation and for creating synergies. Lastly, a new meeting was proposed to take place to discuss among other developing together a new potential pilot case of ENVISION focused on vineyards.

The FIRE project representatives described their “Evangelists programme”. ENVISION’s partners were invited to attend the Fire Forum and asked to disseminate it which has been fully supported by the ENVISION dissemination team. They promised to invite ENVISION next year providing a slot because unfortunately this year were already booked. Moreover, they explained their close collaboration with Copa Cogeca. Clustering events of ENVISION and FIRE will be considered in the future. A policy session together was proposed by AGROAPPS and FIRE accepted that this is a desirable option. Furthermore, the “Evangelist of agriculture” might make a presentation in one of the ENVISION workshops. The projects agreed for mutual support on social media and newsletters, and FIRE asked ENVISION to be a contributor to their work in the field of agriculture.

MEF4CAP team said that they are interested in some of the outputs of ENVISION and they have already read the project information on the ENVISION website. Lots of areas were discussed following the MEF4CAP representatives’ questions. These were the Data Cube of ENVISION, the storage and

processing activities, the area monitoring ambition, the small parcels monitoring, the satellite images with a perspective 5 to 10 years from now, the limitations of Sentinels, the possibilities of the geo-tagged photos and UAVs, the satellites' possibilities for detections of more activities than now, the open technologies and products, and the in-situ data. MEF4CAP representatives mentioned demonstrations 1 and 4 of their project as a good possibility for cooperation. They said that they would be happy to continue the collaboration, share deliverables, and organize joint events. ENVISION team asked if there is availability of the MEF4CAP deliverables, as well as if the Annual Report templates' developers of DG AGRI and Managing Authorities of Rural Development Programmes are engaged to MEF4CAP.

SEN4CAP has been formally closed last March. Nevertheless, they still continue the support to the users. Their team commented about their collaboration with the NIVA project. Moreover, they briefed the ENVISION team about their final events that took place in March, the new webinars planned for July and September, and they mentioned the availability of plenty of information on their website. Regarding ENVISION, they asked about the business cases and how exactly they are defined. Another question concerned how ENVISION plans to build upon other projects and if ENVISION has started from scratch. Also, they raised a question in regard to the user requirements and the specificities of very small countries. ENVISION proposed a meeting between technical teams of the two projects, as well as the organisation of a webinar and a joint publication. The SEN4CAP team said that they are ready to provide their feedback on anything ENVISION would like to report to them. ENVISION mentioned the problem faced in regard to the download of images that are archived and relevant to this an online meeting at the end of June was agreed to discuss how they can provide help. SEN4CAP proposed to the ENVISION team to submit questions on the SEN4CAP forum as they are still maintaining it, as well as they stressed that they are willing to discuss any win-win collaboration. The last topic of discussion was the availability and speed of responses of ESA to requests.

6 Next steps

This deliverable will be presented in the next monthly project meeting on July 6 and feedback from the ENVISION partners will be collected. Moreover, the coordinator and author will wait for the immediate comments and advice of the Project Officer, and together with the WP2 leader, a possible new round of meetings will be discussed.

The next relevant deliverable D6.5 “Collaboration with EU projects and initiatives (2)” is due in month 20 and will further elaborate on the solutions derived from the projects, the ENVISION strengths and potential contributions from the other projects.

This final version of the deliverable will include a final update with regards to the liaison connections with the selected projects.

End of Document

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869366.